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**Exploring the Impact of Leadership Styles
on Perceived Cultural Change Among
Employees Post-Acquisition**

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Executive Summary

Eighteen months into Cummins Inc.'s ownership, cultural integration on the Roermond shop floor remains patchy. To discover why, 150 employees rated the leadership they receive from both supervisors and managers, how they sense the "Cummins shift", and their willingness to feel and embrace new work practices. Nine department focus groups then traced tangible "before-and-after" moments from new uniforms to safety huddles and debated what makes change credible.

The evidence converges on a single chain: when frontline leaders act transformationally, explaining the purpose behind change, listening, and recognising effort, employees perceive authentic cultural change, resulting in a significant drop in resistance. Where leadership is transactional or absent, culture talk is dismissed as cosmetic, and push-back rises. Mediation analysis shows that employees' perception of culture change carries two-thirds of leadership's total impact on resistance, while trust amplifies the effect, which is earned chiefly through visible, on-the-line presence.

Two sequential moves would close the gap. In the next six months, the plant must repair credibility by mandating weekly line-side presence for every supervisor and manager, delivering short micro-coaching sessions on vision framing and feedback, closing each suggestion within thirty days, and refreshing visible symbols so employees can see Cummins' values. Once those habits are established, the following eighteen months should embed them: each department will track a concise culture dashboard, leadership-style metrics will enter the annual 360-degree review, cross-functional swaps will spread good practice, and every frontline leader will complete the Percipio "Skills Builder – Leadership" Aspire Journey (Cummins Global Learning Platform). Meeting

these milestones will aid in lifting transformational-leadership scores, cut resistance below the current benchmark and unlock the full strategic value of the acquisition.

Abstract

This thesis explores the impact of leadership styles on perceived cultural change and resistance to change among blue-collar employees at Cummins Emission Solutions (CES) in Roermond, following its acquisition by Cummins Inc. in October 2023. 150 employees rated supervisory and managerial leadership style (MLQ), perceived cultural change (PCC), resistance to change (RTC), Organisational Culture (OCAI), and Leadership Trust (LT). Nine department focus groups supplied contextual depth. Confirmatory factor analysis supported five distinct constructs. Hierarchical regressions showed transformational leadership predicted stronger PCC ($\beta = 0.44, p < .001$) and lower RTC both directly ($\beta = -0.20, p = .002$) and indirectly via PCC ($\beta = -0.16, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.23, -0.08]$). Focus-group narratives confirmed that visible, credible supervisory actions converted culture talk into tangible practice. Findings extend readiness-for-change theory by measuring PCC as the mediating factor and deliver a staged action plan for frontline leaders.

Keywords: *leadership style, organisational culture, resistance to change, shopfloor employees, mergers and acquisitions*

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Introduction

Organisational culture plays a critical role in shaping employee behaviour, motivation, and performance, particularly during periods of transition such as mergers and acquisitions (Schein, 2010). When two organisational entities combine, aligning values, norms, and practices is often one of the most challenging and consequential aspects of post-merger integration (Buono & Bowditch, 1989; Marks & Mirvis, 2011). Leadership, especially at the supervisory and managerial level, is central to managing this cultural alignment, as it directly influences how employees perceive and respond to change (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Kotter, 1996). Yet, while prior research often centers on top management's role in cultural transformation, the experiences and perceptions of shopfloor employees who are typically most affected by operational shifts are frequently underrepresented in empirical inquiry.

This study focuses on Cummins Emission Solutions (CES) in Roermond, an American production facility that was acquired in October 2023 by Cummins Inc. from Faurecia, a French automotive supplier. From exploratory interviews conducted during the study with managers and the management ($N= 11$), before the acquisition, the plant was characterised by a culture which deemed production a priority over employees and stressed on financial gains at the cost of employee wellbeing following a series of unsuccessful production launches which led to the plant being deemed as a “crisis” plant until its acquisition. This had a cascading effect, which resulted in little to no employee autonomy and the presence of a “fear culture” wherein employees were reluctant to speak up. Cummins Inc. has been actively trying to change this persisting negative culture to a more positive, open, “fearless” culture, encouraging the adaptation of Cummins values, which symbolise open, honest, and transparent communication and respect for everyone.

Due to compliance restrictions and the unavailability of hard data, further statistical backing for this claim is not available. However, preliminary organisational surveys (Cummins HR, personal communication, February 2025) during the early months post-acquisition have suggested a discrepancy in how cultural change is perceived within the company: while top management views the transition as culturally positive and progressing, shopfloor employees report limited or no perceived change. This divergence raises important questions regarding how leadership behaviours, particularly those of frontline supervisors and department managers, affect employee engagement, adaptation, and cultural alignment during organisational transformation.

Leadership style, broadly defined as the pattern of behaviours used by leaders to influence and manage people (Northouse, 2018), is an essential lens through which to explore this phenomenon. The Full-Range Leadership Theory (Bass & Avolio, 1994) distinguishes between transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership. Transformational leaders focus on vision, motivation, and individual development, and have been strongly associated with effective change implementation (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Transactional leaders, on the other hand, emphasise structured rewards and performance monitoring, while laissez-faire leaders reflect a passive or avoidant approach. Each of these styles may shape how employees perceive cultural change, trust leadership, or resist new norms (Oreg, 2006; Piderit, 2000).

McGrath's three-horned dilemma reminds organisational researchers that no single study can maximise control, realism and generalisability at once (McGrath, 1981). This study addresses the trade-off by combining three mutually reinforcing methods to understand the relationship between supervisory leadership styles and perceived cultural change among shopfloor employees at CES Roermond. The plant-wide survey (N = 150)

sacrifices some contextual nuance but delivers the statistical breadth needed for generalisable claims about leadership style, cultural change and resistance. Two-stage focus groups restore realism: by observing employees first without and then with their supervisor present, the study captures how the same leadership behaviour is framed in everyday shop-floor interactions. Finally, semi-structured interviews with managers supply an element of control, linking employee reports to the intentions and policies that shape them. Together, these strands create a balanced platform from which to evaluate operational-level leadership during post-acquisition integration.

By centring the perceptions and experiences of shopfloor employees, this study addresses a critical gap in organisational change research and offers actionable insights into how leadership at the operational level can facilitate or hinder cultural integration. The findings contribute to both academic literature and the practical efforts of Cummins to foster a more cohesive post-acquisition culture.

Research question

How and to what extent does leadership style shape employees perceived cultural change and resistance to change during the first year after the Cummins–Faurecia acquisition?

Literature Review

Organisational culture and leadership are tightly interwoven, especially during periods of significant transformation such as mergers and acquisitions (Schein, 1985). The process of cultural change is complex, often nonlinear, and shaped by the perceptions, actions, and reactions of individuals across all hierarchical levels (Schein, 2010). While strategic vision and executive alignment are crucial for steering cultural change, implementation and day-to-day reinforcement typically occur at the frontline where supervisors act as the primary interface between organisational strategy and employee experience (Kotter, 1996; Bass & Avolio, 1994). This literature review examines how different leadership styles influence perceived cultural change and employee resistance during organisational transitions.

Organisational Culture, Leadership and Change

Organisational culture encompasses shared assumptions, values, and beliefs that guide behaviour within a group (Schein, 2010). These cultural elements are embedded in daily routines, communication styles, and leadership behaviours, making culture both persistent and difficult to reshape. During acquisitions, cultural integration often becomes a key determinant of post-merger success or failure (Buono & Bowditch, 1989; Stahl & Voigt, 2008). Misalignment between old and new organisational values may lead to confusion, uncertainty, or resistance among employees, particularly in production environments where operational routines are closely tied to identity and stability (Marks & Mirvis, 2011), which has been conspicuous in the plant. Culture change does not occur through policy declarations alone. It requires sustained behavioural modelling, symbolic reinforcement, and alignment of systems with desired values (Schein, 2010). This process

is often disrupted when leadership at different levels communicates inconsistent expectations or fails to acknowledge employee concerns. In such cases, shopfloor employees may struggle to recognise or internalise the desired cultural shift.

There exists ample evidence which signifies that leadership is a strong factor influencing culture change. According to Bass and Avolio's (1994) Full-Range Leadership Theory, leadership styles can be broadly categorised as transformational, transactional, or laissez-faire. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate followers through a shared vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualised support. They are frequently cited as the most effective drivers of cultural and organisational change (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Transactional leaders, on the other hand, emphasise structure, task completion, and reward-based supervision. While transactional leadership is useful in maintaining short-term performance and operational clarity, it may lack the inspirational or developmental qualities necessary to drive deeper cultural transformation (Bass, 1990). Laissez-faire leadership is characterised by a lack of guidance or decision-making, often resulting in role ambiguity and organisational inertia (Bass & Avolio, 1994). This passive style has been associated with increased employee dissatisfaction, uncertainty, and resistance to change (Skogstad et al., 2007). In post-acquisition settings, leadership behaviours at the supervisory and managerial level become especially critical. They are not only responsible for translating abstract corporate goals into practical action but also for modelling cultural norms in their daily interactions with employees (Kotter & Schlesinger, 1979). Research by Schweiger and Goulet (2005) and Marks and Mirvis (2011) suggests that when supervisors engage in two-way communication, demonstrate empathy, and embody the new culture through their behaviours, employees are more likely to perceive change positively and resist less. Inconsistent or misaligned leadership

styles can therefore exacerbate resistance and hinder cultural integration, even when top management perceives change as successful.

Adaptive Leadership in Transitions

Beyond the Full-Range Leadership Model, similar to transformational leadership style is the concept of adaptive leadership, which offers additional insight into how leaders navigate complex, uncertain change environments. Adaptive leadership involves mobilising people to tackle tough challenges and thrive amidst transformation (Heifetz et al., 2009). Unlike technical leadership, which relies on predefined solutions, adaptive leadership emphasises listening, experimentation, and facilitating collective problem-solving. In production settings, adaptive and transformational leadership may be expressed through frontline supervisors who empower employees to suggest improvements, acknowledge uncertainty, and jointly co-create responses to evolving demands. These behaviours can reinforce a sense of agency, reduce resistance, and help employees interpret organisational change not as a top-down imposition but as a shared learning process (Uhl-Bien et al., 2007).

Employee Perception, Cognition, and Resistance to Change

Employee perception is not merely a passive reflection of leadership action; it is an active cognitive process shaped by prior experiences, expectations, and interpretations. According to Oreg (2006), resistance to change is both dispositional and situational. Employees may resist change not only due to fear of loss or uncertainty but also when they perceive the process as illegitimate or misaligned with organisational values. This aligns with Piderit's (2000) model of ambivalence, where cognitive, emotional, and

intentional components of resistance interact dynamically. Employees are more likely to accept change when they feel heard, when leadership is perceived as consistent and trustworthy, and when the rationale for change is transparent (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999). Trust acts as a moderating variable between leadership style and change receptivity; a dynamic that aligns with Leader–Member Exchange (LMX) theory, which stresses that the quality of relational exchanges between leaders and employees shapes how followers respond to their leader’s influence (Gerstner & Day, 1997). High-quality LMX relationships, characterised by mutual respect and open communication, have been linked to lower resistance and higher engagement (Gerstner & Day, 1997). Taken together, these findings make it essential to assess leadership not only through leaders’ self-reports but also through employees’ sense-making. The departmental focus groups in this study serve that purpose, allowing workers to describe how day-to-day exchanges with supervisors shape their judgment of whether the change is legitimate, consistent, and worthy of support.

Research Gap

Despite the central role of supervisors in organisational change, there is a lack of empirical studies that examine how different leadership styles at ground level involving production line supervisors and managers influence employee-perceived cultural change, particularly in production environments. Even fewer studies apply a mixed-methods design that integrates quantitative perception data with qualitative behavioural observations and managerial self-administered assessments. The current study addresses this gap by exploring how supervisors’ leadership styles affect shopfloor employees’ perception of cultural change and resistance following the acquisition of CES Roermond

by Cummins Inc. Perceived cultural change (PCC) is theorised to shape resistance to change (RTC) because it alters the legitimacy and uncertainty appraisals that underlie employees' reactions to change initiatives. When workers can point to concrete, values-consistent shifts in daily practice, visible rituals, new decision rules, and credible symbols, change appears legitimate and purposeful, lowering the uncertainty that typically feeds resistance (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999; Dent & Goldberg, 1999). Conversely, when employees judge the culture message as cosmetic or inconsistent with lived reality, cognitive, emotional, and intentional ambivalence emerges (Piderit, 2000), heightening the dispositional and situational resistance processes described by Oreg (2006). Although this PCC → RTC link is not one of the formal hypotheses, exploring it offers a theoretically grounded lens for interpreting why transformational leadership, which tends to make cultural change tangible, often coincides with lower resistance, whereas transactional or laissez-faire supervision does not (Figure 1.c).

Hypotheses

Based on the theoretical framework, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H1: Leadership Style and Perceived Cultural Change

Employees who perceive their supervisors as transformational leaders will report a greater sense of cultural change compared to employees under transactional or laissez-faire leadership, who will perceive weaker cultural change (Figure 1.a). (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Eagly, Johannesen-Schmidt, & Van Engen, 2003)

H2: Leadership Style and Resistance to Change

Employees under transformational leadership will exhibit lower resistance to change as compared to employees under transactional or laissez-faire leadership, who will show higher resistance to change (Figure 1.b). (Dent & Goldberg, 1999; Oreg, 2006)

Figure 1

Hypotheses presented in this study

1.a H1

1.b H2

1.c

Note: **1.a.** Direct effect of supervisory leadership style on employees *perceived cultural change* (PCC). A solid arrow labelled **Transformational (+)** indicates the hypothesised positive association (higher PCC), whereas **Transactional / Laissez-faire (-)** indicates the hypothesised negative association (lower PCC). **1.b.** Direct effect of supervisory leadership style on employees' *resistance to change* (RTC). The solid arrow **Transformational (-)** denotes the expected reduction in resistance, while **Transactional / Laissez-faire (+)** denotes the expected increase. **1.c.** Exploratory mediation model. The two solid arrows reproduce the hypothesised paths from Panels 1.a and 1.b. The dotted arrow labelled **Exploratory (-)** tests, post hoc, whether PCC carries part of the transformational-leadership effect to RTC. This indirect path was not part of the formal hypotheses and is treated as supplemental evidence. *Note.* MLQ = Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (transformational leadership); PCC = Perceived Cultural Change; RTC = Resistance to Change. "(+)" indicates an expected positive association with the outcome variable; "(-)" indicates an expected negative association.

Method

Design

A concurrent explanatory-sequential mixed-methods design involving surveys and focus groups was used to test the hypothesised relations statistically and substantiate them with employees' narratives. The quantitative strand consisted of a plant-wide survey; the qualitative strand used department-level focus groups and interviews for elaboration.

Participants

All employees at Cummins Emission Solutions (Roermond) were invited ($N = 325$). One hundred and fifty valid questionnaires were returned ($N = 150$). Respondents came from three job functions: Shopfloor ($n = 56$), Office/Management ($n = 50$), Supervisors/Managers ($n = 44$) and seven focal departments (MSO1–3, PC&L, Maintenance, Quality, ME). Small support units (e.g., Finance, HR, IT) were collapsed into "Other support" to protect anonymity.

Sample Size and Power

Using G*Power 3.1, I conducted an a-priori power analysis for a multiple-regression test of a single standardised slope (two-tailed, $\alpha = .05$), a sample of $N = 150$ with five predictors affords 66 % power to detect a small-to-medium effect ($f^2 = .04$, $\beta \approx 0.20$, the size of the MLQ \rightarrow RTC slope). For the larger MLQ \rightarrow PCC path ($\beta \approx 0.44$, $f^2 \approx 0.25$), power exceeds 0.95, indicating that the study is sufficiently powered for the main hypothesised effects but underpowered for very small coefficients.

Measures

To keep the questionnaire concise yet theoretically complete, I paired well-established scales with a purpose-built measure of perceived cultural change (Table 1). The six-item MLQ short form covers the transformational–transactional spectrum that anchors my two hypotheses (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Because Cummins aims to foster a clan-type culture of openness and teamwork, five clan items from the OCAI serve as a validated benchmark (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). For PCC, I wrote four items that reflect the specific post-acquisition conditions on the Roermond shop floor: visible shifts in safety rituals, communication tone, and decision latitude; so, no separate cognitive-interview stage was needed. Resistance to change is indexed by Oreg’s five-item RTC scale, and a four-item leadership-trust measure (Rousseau, 1989) captures the relational context that can amplify or dampen leadership effects. All five instruments show acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha, \omega \geq 0.70$) and load cleanly on five distinct factors (CFA: CFI = 0.93, SRMR = .064, RMSEA = 0.056, using the diagonally weighted least squares (DWLS) estimator, which models the polychoric correlation matrix and provides robust standard errors for the ordinal five-point items. All subsequent CFA results refer to this DWLS solution), providing a sound measurement base for the subsequent analyses.

Table 1

Overview of Constructs used in this study

Construct (items)	Sample item	α	ω	Source
Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) (6)	“My supervisor talks optimistically about the future.”	0.77	0.81	Bass & Avolio (1994)
Organisational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) (5)	“The work environment feels like a supportive community.”	0.72	0.74	Cameron & Quinn (2011)
Perceived Cultural Change (PCC) (4)	“Since the acquisition I notice significant cultural changes.”	0.80	0.81	Developed for this study
Resistance to Change (RTC) (5)	“I generally feel uncomfortable with changes in the workplace.”	0.70	0.70	Oreg (2006)
Leadership Trust (LT) (4)	“I trust my supervisor’s leadership in guiding the team through change.”	0.86	0.87	Rousseau (1989)

Note: Cronbach’s α and McDonald’s ω are from the JASP reliability output; all $\alpha \geq 0.70$.

A five-factor CFA showed acceptable fit, $\chi^2(242) = 608.52, p < .001$, DWLS estimator; SRMR = 0.064, CFI = 0.93.

Procedure

Survey (March-May 2025): An Online survey was sent out plant-wide using Qualtrics, and an offline paper version was made available in the plant canteens. Both distribution methods had the survey available in three languages (Dutch, English, and German).

Focus groups and interviews (April–May 2025): Nine department-specific groups with two sessions each (5–6 participants) (N= 46) were carried out using a quadrant-timeline exercise (see Figure 2) to elicit change narratives; comments were captured on colour-coded post-its rather than audio recording to maximise psychological safety. After structuring the two-stage sessions (first without, then with the supervisor and manager present), I generated each group’s invite list as follows: an Excel sheet of all shop-floor names was randomised with the =RAND() function, the first ten names per supervisor were retained, and department managers were asked to pull 5–6 volunteers from that shortlist whose release would not disrupt production. Thus, every participant came from the same random pool while still meeting shift-coverage constraints. Interviews with the managers and plant leadership team were carried out to better understand the background of the plant and its functioning from before the acquisition until the present.

Figure 2

Diagram depicting the quadrant timeline used for the focus group sessions.

Qualitative analysis

Focus-group notes were coded with Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase procedure (phases 1–6) (Refer to the appendix). Latent themes (e.g., *Perceived absence of leadership presence*) were cross-tabulated with departmental means, triangulating qualitative insights with Model 1 effect sizes.

Ethics

The study was approved by the Radboud University Social Sciences Ethics Committee (*Ref.* ECSW-LT-2025-3-6-61434). A completed Data Management Protocol (*version* WOH 2023) is lodged with the department repository (RU). Participation was voluntary, GDPR-compliant, and anonymous; focus-group notes contained no direct identifiers.

Results

This chapter reports the quantitative findings and the qualitative focus-group insights side-by-side. Results are organised in four steps: data screening, descriptive statistics and correlations enriched with focus-group observations, hypothesis tests with integrated narrative evidence, and an overall mixed-methods synthesis.

Data screening

Less than 2 % of data were missing per scale; pairwise deletion was applied. All variables were approximately normal ($|\text{skew}| < 0.9$, $|\text{kurtosis}| < 1.1$) and no multivariate outliers were detected (Mahalanobis $p > .001$). Variance-inflation factors were < 2 in every regression, indicating negligible multicollinearity.

Assumption checks: Multivariate normality was acceptable (Mardia's skew = 2.17, kurtosis = 9.34). Box's M was non-significant, $F(55, 4\ 549.3) = 1.18$, $p = .11$, supporting homogeneity of covariance for the MANOVA. Levene tests were non-significant for all univariate ANOVAs (all $p > 0.10$).

Although the omnibus MANOVA indicated no reliable multivariate effect of job function on the combined outcome set, $F_{\text{Wilks}}(6, 286) = 1.01$, $p = .39$, I retained binary job-function dummies (shop-floor operator, supervisor, office/management) in all regression and mediation models for two reasons. First, role expectations can shape both leadership perceptions and change receptivity; partialling out their variance reduces omitted-variable bias even when overall mean differences are small. Second, the MANOVA had limited sensitivity to detect effects smaller than $f^2 = 0.06$, whereas including the covariates protects against Type II error without inflating Type I error

because each model still satisfies the recommended $N \geq 20k$ rule of thumb. All reported MLQ, PCC, and RTC coefficients are therefore adjusted for job function.

Descriptive statistics, correlations, and first qualitative impressions

Table 2 shows mean, standard deviations, reliabilities, and zero-order correlations. Transformational leadership (MLQ) correlated positively with perceived cultural change (PCC) and clan-type culture (OCAI) and negatively with resistance to change (RTC). Leadership trust (LT) displayed the strongest bivariate link with MLQ ($r = 0.60, p < .001$) and a substantial negative link with RTC ($r = -0.45, p < .001$).

Focus-group talk echoed these patterns. Operators in MSO 3 repeatedly credited their supervisor for “talking us through every tweak” and “walking the line every day,” reflecting the department’s above-average MLQ ($M = 3.29$) and lowest RTC ($M = 2.64$). In contrast, MSO 2 workers described leadership as “invisible” and “not listening,” mirroring low MLQ ($M = 2.88$) and high RTC ($M = 3.12$).

Table 2

Descriptive statistics, reliabilities, and Pearson correlations (N = 150)

Variable	M	SD	α	1	2	3	4
MLQ	3.20	0.88	0.77	—			
OCAI	2.90	0.55	0.72	0.23	—		
PCC	3.27	0.77	0.80	0.28	0.44	—	
RTC	2.48	0.68	0.70	-0.35	-0.41	-0.48	—

Variable	M	SD	α	1	2	3	4
LT	3.23	0.91	0.86	0.60	0.31	0.47	-0.45

Note. $p < 0.01$; two-tailed. Correlations reproduce the JASP matrix; descriptive moments are weighted composites of job-function means.

One-way MANOVA (MLQ, PCC, OCAI, LT, RTC) by department was significant, Wilks' $\lambda = 0.787$, $F(22, 274) = 1.59$, $p = .049$. Follow-up ANOVAs showed the largest departmental spread for MLQ ($\eta^2 = .11$) and RTC ($\eta^2 = .09$).

Hypothesis-testing strategy

Analyses were run in JASP 0.18. All continuous variables were mean-centred.

1. **Hierarchical regressions.** Job-function and department dummies entered at Step 1; predictors at Step 2. Multicollinearity was negligible (max VIF = 1.56).
2. **Mediation analyses.** Three lavaan models (5000 bootstrap samples) evaluated:
 - **Model 1** MLQ \rightarrow PCC \rightarrow RTC (controls: job function).
 - **Model 2** MLQ \rightarrow PCC \rightarrow OCAI.
 - **Model 3** LT \rightarrow MLQ (\pm PCC).

(Standardised paths, bootstrap CIs, and R^2 are summarised in *Table 3*.)

3. **Integration.** Quantitative patterns were juxtaposed with focus-group themes following a weaving approach (refer to discussion).

Table 3*Standardised mediation results (bootstrap 95 % CIs, N = 150)*

Model / Path	β	SE	z	95 % CI	p	R² (DV)
1 MLQ → RTC (total)	-0.35	0.06	-5.68	-0.48, -0.23	<0.001	0.26
Direct	-0.20	0.06	-3.12	-0.32, -0.07	0.002	
Indirect (MLQ → PCC → RTC)	-0.16	0.04	-4.15	-0.23, -0.08	<0.001	
2 MLQ → OCAI (total)	0.23	0.04	5.24	0.14, 0.32	<0.001	0.19
Direct	0.10	0.04	2.34	0.02, 0.18	0.019	
Indirect (via PCC)	0.13	0.03	4.56	0.08, 0.19	<0.001	
3 LT → MLQ (total)	0.61	0.05	11.68	0.51, 0.72	<0.001	0.48
Direct	0.61	0.07	9.05	0.48, 0.74	<0.001	
Indirect (LT → PCC → MLQ)	0.00	0.04	0.06	-0.08, 0.09	0.954	

Note: Path estimates reproduce the lavaan output. All indirect effects were bias-corrected using lavaan's bias-corrected bootstrap.

Figure 3

Standardised mediation models (N = 150)

Note: Model 1 tests the indirect effect of transformational leadership (MLQ) on resistance to change (RTC) through perceived cultural change (PCC). Model 2 tests the indirect effect of transformational leadership on clan-type culture (OCAI) through PCC. Model 3 examines the direct effect of leadership trust (LT) on transformational leadership with PCC entered as a potential mediator. Solid arrows depict the paths constituting each indirect effect; dotted arrows show the residual direct path after the mediator is included. Values on the arrows are completely standardised regression coefficients (β) followed by 95 % bias-corrected bootstrap confidence intervals (5000 samples). Job-function dummy variables were entered as covariates in Models 1 and 2; no covariates were used in Model 3. All continuous variables were mean-centred. $***p < .001$. $*p < .05$. ns = non-significant.

Group differences

A one-way MANOVA with department as the independent variable and MLQ, PCC, OCAI, LT, and RTC as dependents was significant, Wilks' $\lambda = 0.79$, $F(22, 274) = 1.59$, $p = .049$, partial $\eta^2 = .10$. Follow-up ANOVAs showed the greatest spread for MLQ ($\eta^2 = .11$) and RTC ($\eta^2 = .09$). Focus-group testimony explains those numbers:

- MSO 1: Phrases such as “all talk, no action” captured a lingering “Faurecia mindset,” matching below-average MLQ (3.04) and elevated RTC (3.01).
- PC&L: employees felt “thrown under the bus,” aligning with low PCC (2.94) and the dataset's highest RTC (3.16).
- MSO 3: positive supervisor presence (“really good communication”) explained higher LT (3.67) and lower RTC (2.64).

Hypothesis tests with qualitative corroboration

H1: Leadership style and perceived cultural change

Hierarchical regression controlling for department showed that transformational leadership predicted greater PCC ($\beta = 0.44$, $p < .001$; $\Delta R^2 = 0.43$). Focus-group accounts illuminate the mechanism; in MSO 3, visible supervisor behaviour, daily walk-arounds, and rapid feedback made Cummins culture “feel real,” whereas MSO 2 and PC&L participants said, “nothing has changed except the logo,” explaining their low PCC scores.

H2: Leadership style and resistance to change

Transformational leadership predicted lower RTC directly ($\beta = -0.20$, $p = .002$) and indirectly through PCC ($\beta = -0.16$, 95 % CI [-0.23, -0.08]). Qualitative data corroborated the mediation: when employees could name concrete cultural shifts

(uniforms, safety rituals), they framed change as “progress”; when they saw only “paper promises,” they described change as disruptive, fuelling resistance.

Supplementary mediation results

Model 2 confirmed that PCC transmits the positive impact of leadership on OCAI (indirect $\beta = 0.13, p < .001$). Model 3 showed leadership trust strongly predicts MLQ ($\beta = 0.61, p < .001$) but is not channelled through PCC (indirect $\beta \approx 0$). Focus-group remarks clarify why trust depends on managers’ and supervisors’ day-to-day presence, not on abstract cultural messages.

Latent themes and quantitative links

Thematic clustering across departments produced four latent themes: Perceived Absence of Leadership Presence, Poor Communication Loops, Distrust in Strategic Direction, and Surface-Level Culture Change. Appendix maps each theme to departmental means on MLQ, PCC and RTC. Departments scoring high on “Absence of Leadership Presence” consistently showed the MLQ ↓ / RTC ↑ profile observed in the quantitative data, reinforcing H1 and H2.

Summary

All quantitative hypotheses were supported and richly explained by focus-group narratives. Departments differ not because employees inherently welcome or reject change, but because supervisory conduct shapes whether culture change feels authentic. The next chapter discusses the theoretical and practical implications for post-acquisition integration at Cummins Roermond.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explain why some shop-floor units at Cummins Roermond absorb the post-acquisition culture quickly, whereas others continue to resist day-to-day change. By combining survey data ($N = 150$) with nine department-level focus groups, we captured both the statistical pattern and the lived experience of integration.

Interpretation of the findings

Transformational leadership emerged as an influential factor in cultural acceptance. Across departments, higher MLQ scores predicted a stronger personal sense of cultural change (PCC) and, through that perception, lower resistance to change (RTC). These findings replicate classic change-readiness models that position leadership vision and individual sense-making as sequential levers (Armenakis & Harris, 1993; Kotter, 1996). The direct MLQ \rightarrow RTC path, although weaker than the indirect route, remained significant, suggesting that inspirational behaviour can attenuate resistance.

Leadership trust (LT) did not operate through PCC but had a strong, direct link to MLQ. Focus-group narratives clarified why: employees judge trustworthiness largely on supervisors' visible presence, timely feedback and consistency elements also highlighted in transformational theory (Bass & Avolio, 1994) and high-trust models of organisational change (Rousseau, 1989).

Departmental contrasts reinforced the mechanism. MSO 3, where supervisors walk the line daily and celebrate small wins, posted the highest MLQ and the lowest RTC; PC&L and MSO 2, where leadership is "seen only when something breaks," showed the

opposite profile. This pattern matches empirical work on the line-manager influence in cross-cultural acquisitions (Sarala et al., 2019) and on resistance stemming from uncertain supervisory direction (Oreg, 2006).

The integration reveals a single explanatory chain: *Visible, credible supervisory actions* → *Employees recognise tangible culture change* (“*We finally see Cummins ways on the floor*”) → *Psychological safety rises, resistance falls*. Conversely, where supervisors are absent or transactional, employees perceive no real shift, interpret top-down messages as empty rhetoric, and resist new procedures.

Taken together, the evidence supports a simple chain: ***trustworthy transformational acts*** → ***recognised culture change*** → ***lower resistance***. Conversely, transactional or laissez-faire behaviour leaves the cultural message unconvincing, and resistance persists.

Theoretical implications

The study extends transformational-leadership theory by confirming its relevance in a real-time, post-acquisition setting, an environment where many models focus instead on top-team signalling or HR artefacts (Birkinshaw et al., 2000). It also integrates cultural change and resistance literatures, empirically demonstrating the mediating role of *perceived* culture change, a construct often theorised (Beer & Nohria, 2000) but seldom measured.

Practical implications: A staged action plan

Supervisory and managerial behaviour turned out to be the decisive lever in converting cultural rhetoric into everyday reality. Survey results showed that transformational leadership predicted stronger perceptions of cultural change and lower resistance, while focus-group participants traced their acceptance or scepticism directly to what supervisors and managers did on the shopfloor. A two-stage sequence is consistent with established change-management theory. Kotter's (1996) eight-step model argues that leaders must first create credibility and short-term wins before they can anchor new behaviours in routine practice, while Lewin's (1951) classic "unfreeze-change-refreeze" framework likewise separates an initial readiness phase from subsequent institutionalisation. Empirical reviews underline the point: Beer and Nohria's (2000) comparison of "Theory E" (economic) and "Theory O" (organisational) programmes shows that early, visible signals of commitment such as line-side presence and rapid feedback loops are prerequisites for deeper cultural embedding, and Armenakis and Bedeian (1999) list "supervisor credibility" as a primary antecedent of change acceptance. In our data, departments that saw supervisors daily (MSO 3) already satisfied this credibility condition and showed low resistance, whereas units with "drive-by" leadership (PC&L, MSO 2) had not yet "unfrozen". Stage 1, therefore, focuses on rebuilding trust through walk-the-line visibility, micro-coaching, and fast suggestion closure. Stage 2 mirrors Kotter's consolidation steps by hard-wiring the same behaviours through culture dashboard, 360° feedback, cross-functional swaps so that they persist beyond individual leaders. Framing the interventions in this staged way thus aligns the practice

recommendations with well-supported theoretical and empirical guidance on how durable culture change unfolds.

Stage 1 (Short-term) (0 – 6 months): The immediate priority is to rebuild credibility and visibility, where employees reported an “absence of leadership presence.” Four low-cost moves address that gap:

1. **Walk-the-Line Friday:** Each manager, along with the supervisor, spends two uninterrupted hours on the line every week, logging at least two two-way conversations on the “culture topic” of the month. *Rationale:* Visible presence and dialogue restore the “communicator credibility” lever that theory links to early change acceptance (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999).
2. **Micro-coaching cycle:** Four focused workshops on vision framing, rapid feedback, bite-sized recognition and conflict repair, followed by brief peer-shadow sessions. *Rationale:* These micro-skills map directly onto the transformational behaviours that lifted MLQ scores in the high-performing MSO 3 department.
3. **Thirty-day feedback loop:** Every suggestion card (verbal or FiFi – Find It, Fix It) must be adopted, adapted or declined with reasons, within 30 days. *Rationale:* Closing the loop tackles the “poor communication” theme that fuelled resistance in PC&L and signals that management acts on employee voice.
4. **Visible-symbol refresh:** Issue Cummins equipment, update red-tag boards and revamp existing instruments and logistics with the Cummins brand. *Rationale:* Tangible cues translate abstract values into everyday artefacts, countering the “surface-level change” scepticism voiced in several focus groups.

Stage 2 (Long-term) (6 – 24 months): Once trust and visibility have improved, the task is to embed the same behaviours in routines that survive staff turnover. Four structural moves serve that purpose:

1. **Culture dashboard:** Every department co-defines three KPI symbols and one monthly ritual, displayed on its Andon screen. *Rationale:* Integrating culture metrics into the production scoreboard anchors new norms in the same visual-management rhythm that governs safety and quality.
2. **Annual 360° review:** Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) and leadership-trust items become part of the appraisal cycle, with mid-year progress checks. *Rationale:* Embedding behavioural feedback into HR processes creates accountability and sustains gains after the initial spotlight fades.
3. **Cross-functional swaps:** Monthly exchanges between high- and low-PCC departments, followed by joint debriefs. *Rationale:* Peer modelling diffuses effective practices more credibly than top-down directives and accelerates convergence across the plant.
4. **Leadership-academy pathway:** Enrol all frontline supervisors in Cummins' Percipio learning platform and give them one hour of protected learning time per week to complete the Aspire Journey called "Skills Builder – Leadership" (Cummins Inc., n.d.). Progress is tracked automatically in Percipio and reviewed during the annual 360° appraisal. (Success Indicator: by Month 24, at least 12 supervisors have completed the full Aspire Journey ($\approx 75\%$ of the current supervisor cohort) and can point to one documented shop-floor application that is reflected in team MLQ scores.) *Rationale:* On-demand micro-learning keeps

development alive after workshops end and aligns Roermond with Cummins' global leadership curriculum.

Table 4

Staged intervention plan and evaluation metrics

Horizon	Key lever	Core actions	Target indicators*
0 – 6 mo.	leadership presence & credibility	Walk-the-Line Friday;	MLQ $\geq +0.25$; ≥ 85 % supervisors
		micro-coaching; 30-day	trained; ≥ 70 % suggestions closed
		feedback loop; symbol	on time; ≥ 75 % employees recall \geq
		refresh	2 Cummins values
6 – 24 mo.	Culture routines & structural alignment	Culture dashboard;	MLQ ≥ 3.50 ; RTC ≤ 2.30 ; ≥ 6
		annual 360°; cross-	swaps completed with receiving
		functional swaps;	units; PCC $\geq +0.30$; ≥ 12
		leadership-academy pathway	supervisors complete the Aspire Journey and evidence application

Note: *Indicators are gauged against baseline means and standard deviations from Table 2; MLQ = Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire; RTC = Resistance to Change; PCC = Perceived Cultural Change.

Limitations and future research

The study is cross-sectional; causal claims rely on mediation logic and qualitative convergence rather than true temporal precedence. With 150 participants, the study had

only about 66 % power to detect small effects ($\beta \approx .20$), so relationships weaker than that threshold may have gone undetected. A longitudinal follow-up could test whether the proposed actions move MLQ, PCC, and RTC over time. Second, transactional and laissez-faire leadership were captured only indirectly (inverse MLQ scores). Future work should measure all leadership styles explicitly (Judge & Piccolo, 2004) to assess the hypotheses in-depth to find the right leadership style-company fit. Finally, focus-group participation was voluntary; highly resistant voices may still be under-represented despite anonymity efforts. Further research could also make use of randomised focus-group participant interviews voluntarily.

Mixed-methods contribution

By weaving statistical paths with employee stories, the study answers the call for context-sensitive change research (Cummings & Worley, 2014) and provides Cummins Inc. with an evidence-based playbook that resonates on the factory floor.

Conclusion

Successful post-acquisition integration at Cummins Roermond now hinges less on corporate policies and more on what managers and supervisors say and do each shift. Where frontline leaders act transformationally, explaining the “why,” listening, recognising effort, employees perceive real cultural change, and resistance fades. Where leadership is distant or purely transactional, culture talk rings hollow, and resistance persists. The recommended two-stage action plan, anchored in employee feedback and modest in cost, offers Cummins a practical route to embed its values, accelerate performance gains, and realise the full strategic promise of the plant acquisition. Implementing these steps and tracking the suggested leading indicators will not only strengthen local engagement but also generate learning that Cummins can transfer to other sites undergoing cultural integration. In short, “*culture travels on the feet of supervisors*”; equip those managers and supervisors well, and the rest of the journey becomes markedly easier.

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Appendix

Partial Correlation Table

Variable		MLQ Avg.	OCAI Avg.	PCC Avg.	LT Avg.
1. MLQ Avg.	Pearson's r	—			
	p-value	—			
	Spearman's rho	—			
	p-value	—			
2. OCAI Avg.	Pearson's r	0.233**	—		
	p-value	0.004	—		
	Spearman's rho	0.223**	—		
	p-value	0.006	—		
3. PCC Avg.	Pearson's r	0.276***	0.438***	—	
	p-value	< .001	< .001	—	
	Spearman's rho	0.316***	0.462***	—	
	p-value	< .001	< .001	—	
4. LT Avg.	Pearson's r	0.604***	0.312***	0.465***	—
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	—
	Spearman's rho	0.624***	0.292***	0.466***	—
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	—

Note. Conditioned on variables: RTC Avg. Standard error of effect size (Fisher's z) is currently unavailable for non-parametric partial correlations. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Focus-Group Analysis

Phase	Purpose & researcher actions	Concrete output from this study	Illustrative data/evidence
Familiarisation	Read post-its and observer notes twice; wrote analytic memos per department.	Provisional list of salient expressions (e.g., “Faurecia mindset”, “nothing but a new logo”).	Raw extracts in MSO2: “management not listening”; MSO3: “supervisor talks us through every tweak”.
Generating initial codes	Latent coding	Code book (<i>leader-absence, surface-symbols, two-way-feedback</i>).	Example: comment “Top management still Faurecia-minded” → <i>leader-absence, Faurecia-legacy</i> .
Searching for themes	Grouped codes into candidate themes with mind-mapping; compared across departments.	Six candidate themes: (a) Absence of leadership presence, (b) Faulty feedback loops, (c) Distrust in direction, (d) Surface-level change, (e) Positive supervisor presence, (f) Peer solidarity.	Focus group Post-its showed overlapping of these themes across multiple sessions.
Reviewing themes	Checked coherence of data within themes and distinction between themes; split “Positive supervisor presence” into two facets.	Final four latent themes: Absence of leadership presence, Poor communication loops, Distrust in strategic direction, Surface-level culture change.	All themes met internal homogeneity & external heterogeneity criteria.
Defining & naming themes	Wrote one-paragraph analytic definition for each theme; linked to	Mapping themes and departments with linked	“Absence of leadership presence” defined as “perceived physical or relational invisibility of

Phase	Purpose & researcher actions	Concrete output from this study	Illustrative data/evidence
Producing the report	quantitative variables (MLQ, LT, PCC, RTC). Selected vivid quotes; wove themes into Results narrative; triangulated with mediation models.	survey indicators. Integrated mixed methods Results and Discussion.	supervisors/managers leading to low MLQ/LT and high RTC”. Quote in report: “We are thrown under the bus” (PC&L) illustrates Theme 2 and aligns with lowest PCC (2.94) and highest RTC (3.16).

Note. Theme names and departmental pattern statistics are reproduced from the focus-group analysis.

Survey Questionnaire

Informed Consent:

Thank you for participating in this survey on leadership and cultural change at Cummins Roermond. This study explores how leadership styles impact employees' perceptions of cultural change following the recent acquisition. This survey will take approximately 5 minutes to complete. Your responses are confidential. Participation is voluntary, and you may exit the survey at any time.

Do you agree to participate in this study?

- Yes
- No

Were you employed at this facility before the acquisition (when it was Faurecia)?

- Yes
- No

Are you a contingent employee?

- Yes
- No

How long have you been working at Cummins Roermond?

- Less than 6 months
- 6 months – 1 year
- 1 – 3 years
- More than 3 years

What is your primary job function?

- Shopfloor/Production Employee
- Supervisor/Team Leader
- Office Staff/Management

Which department do you belong to?

- MSO1
- MSO2
- MSO3
- PC&L
- HSE
- Quality
- Finance
- COS
- Maintenance
- ME
- Facilities
- Purchasing/Sales
- HR
- IT

Please indicate how often your direct supervisor or manager demonstrates the following behaviors.

	Never	Sometimes	About half the time	Most of the time	Always
My supervisor talks optimistically about the future of the organization.	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor provides clear goals and expectations for employees.	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor rewards employees for meeting performance targets.	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor takes corrective action only when problems arise.	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor avoids making important decisions.	<input type="radio"/>				
My supervisor supports employees in developing their skills and abilities.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements about the work culture at Cummins Roermond.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
The work environment feels like a collaborative and supportive community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The company encourages innovation and risk-taking.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Management emphasizes efficiency and performance above all else.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Rules and policies govern most decisions in the workplace.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that Cummins' cultural values align with my personal values.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding cultural change at Cummins Roermond.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Since the acquisition, I have noticed significant cultural changes in the workplace.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership has clearly communicated the cultural expectations after the acquisition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that my team has adapted well to the cultural changes introduced by Cummins.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I identify more with the current organizational culture than before the acquisition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements regarding changes at Cummins Roermond.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I generally feel uncomfortable with changes in the workplace.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it difficult to adjust when leadership introduces new policies or procedures.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that the changes at Cummins Roermond will benefit employees in the long run.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that my concerns about cultural change are heard by my supervisor.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it difficult to adapt to the changes introduced since Cummins acquired Faurecia.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements about leadership communication.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
My supervisor effectively communicates the reasons behind cultural changes.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust my supervisor's leadership in guiding the team through organizational change.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Management has been transparent about how the acquisition affects employees.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel that I can openly express concerns about workplace changes to my supervisor.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your own words, how has leadership influenced the cultural changes at Cummins Roermond since changing from Faurecia? Please share any specific experiences or observations.

End of Survey Note:

Thank You for Your Participation! We sincerely appreciate the time and effort you have taken to complete this survey. Your insights are invaluable in helping us understand how leadership influences cultural change at Cummins Roermond. Your responses will contribute to a deeper understanding of how employees experience organizational transitions and how leadership can best support cultural adaptation. By sharing your perspectives, you are helping to shape strategies that foster a more cohesive, engaged, and supportive workplace. If you have any further thoughts or would like to discuss your experiences in more detail, we invite you to participate in follow-up interviews or focus groups. Thank you again for your time and valuable input!